

THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF THE SCIENTIFIC AND SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF EASTERN ALLOMAS IN THE SPIRITUAL FORMATION OF THE INDIVIDUAL

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Annotation: This article describes the importance and role of the scientific and spiritual heritage of Eastern allomas in the spiritual formation of a person, the views of Eastern thinkers and allomas in their works on the acquisition of knowledge, occupation of a person, glorification of high spiritual and moral qualities in him, their content in their works of personality spirituality, High examples of moral etiquette in a person, family.

Key words: national spiritual heritage, Devoni lexicatit turk, Al Farabi's "City of prosperous people", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Qutadgü bilig", Kaykovus "Qobusnoma", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibatul haqoyiq", Saadi's "Gulistan", Jami's "Bahoristan", Alisher Nawai's "Mahbub ulqulub", Davani's "Morali Jaloli".

Our President, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, paid special attention to the education of young people: "we must raise our children ourselves, without leaving them in the hands of someone. To do this, we need to give practical support to talk more with our young people, listen to their hearts, know their pain, solve their problems. In carrying out these tasks, we rely on our national traditions, the rich heritage of our ancestors, which have been formed over the centuries."

We consider it our main task to improve the functioning of all branches of the educational system, based on the requirements of today's era. The study and analysis of the work of Eastern thinkers, the study of his creativity, the study of his views on upbringing are of great practical importance from the point of view of an educator. In their works, they expressed their views on the spirituality of the individual, on the creation of examples of high morality and decency in a person, in a family, on raising

a family, raising children, making ends meet with honest labor, on a rational attitude towards the environment. Thus, the problems of Man and his upbringing, Eastern thinkers, allomas glorify in their works the owner of knowledge, competence, high spiritual and moral qualities of a person, urging everyone to become the owner of such qualities. A generation with a spiritual exaltation, a thorough mastery of modern science, inheriting the rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors, cannot be influenced by any external power, ideas and ideology. The future of people who have brought up such a generation is bright and great.

The mashoyiks say:"the happiness of each nation, the peace and comfort of the states depend on the good upbringing of young people." Also, the well - known Uzbek pedagogue Abdullah Avlani noted that "upbringing is a matter of either life or death or salvation or disaster for us". Abu Rayhon Beruni was one of the first in human history to suggest that children should be taught to work from an early age, raised to honor adult labor, and taught the child to science and the profession should be the focus of the family. Alloma singled out the fact that the Labor Education started in the family should be continued in connection with education at school and teaching a trade. The great thinker carefully studied the inheritance from generation to generation on the basis of Labor and professional succession and highly appreciated the craft activities of people¹. In itself, it is clear that the surreal activity laid the groundwork for the widespread use of ingenuity among artisan Masters in the form of demanding complex labor, deep knowledge. In the work of Mahmud Qoshgariy "Devani lexicatit turk " - listen to his words, doing good to learned, intelligent people. Learning the sciences, the trades, he says. This opinion of alloma encourages people to work, to good, condemns evil. He praises the Masters of Science and craft and calls upon the people to learn from them¹. Sahibqiron Amir Temur attached great importance to the further development of crafts – textiles, wood and stone carving, carpet weaving, pottery, metalworking, and agriculture, livestock and trade, which were separated into an independent sphere on the basis of a large division of labor in his kingdom. Therefore, there was an opportunity for the

emergence of new professions in social life, the path to mass unemployment was not laid. Our ancestors in their works have given a huge emphasis to the professional labor education and upbringing of young people. They approached vocational education as a necessary component of education and training, and believed that it was necessary to carry it along with mental, physical and moral education. Given their abilities and inclinations to young people, one can seriously consider and admonitions about the choice of the type of Labor. CHunonchi says that Alisher Navoi emphasizes the need to take into account the individual, specific abilities of the educated, —even if people are equal in nature, but they are given different qualities. Farabi was the first of the medieval thinkers to develop a whole doctrine of society. His service was universally accepted in the world scientific literature. Farabi has covered a significant number of issues in his works:

1. Topics and tasks of the Social Sciences.
2. Origin, composition and manifestations of social associations.
3. City-state, its functions and forms of government.
4. The place and obligation of a person in society, educational and educational issues.
5. Tasks and ultimate goal of the state association, ways and means of achieving general happiness.

In the science of social life, Farabi introduced urban-state or political science (al-kulikya), jurisprudence (fiqh) and Muslim theology (kalam). The science of ethics and education (pedagogy) should form part of the political sciences and show ways to achieve general happiness. Ethics (ethics) is the knowledge of the actions of members of a society, while political science is the knowledge of the character and control of the actions of all members of society in general. Farabi believes that the management of the state will be of two types: leading the population of the state to real or imaginary happiness. The art of management implies both the theory and the practice of iora. Taking them together gives you the opportunity to properly manage the state, in each specific case, from which some are obtained. In his work farobius,

Phosilus mentions his goals about the community that leads the city to Bliss. The city of Fozil is a city that requires happiness, which leads a whole family to happiness. Adshgan City, on the other hand, demands that his people go to the temporary Zoe. The integration of individuals into society is caused by wars and the use of force, and by people's aspirations to meet their needs. It is necessary for the existence and maturation of people¹. Society is formed from different peoples. The peculiarities and qualities of peoples are explained by Farabi in connection with the features of the geographical conditions in which this or that people live. Farabi divides the city-states into fuzzy or dreamy and ignorant. The dream is such a city that it exists on the basis of the interaction of its inhabitants. The municipality has internal and external functions. In societies that have reached the peak of maturity, there is an opportunity to freely choose a profession. It is here that solitude disappears, and true liberation and equality prevail. Residents of such cities elect their chief, but it can also deprive him of power at any time. The heads of such cities derive from the rule of fairness, equal rights and general welfare in their activities². The boss is a kind of teacher who teaches his students to learn and master ways to achieve happiness. But it is difficult to embody all the requirements in one person, so it is possible to organize the management that will be by the group. In this case, each member of society will have to embody any of these features.

As can be seen from the above, the great alloma and thinkers pay special attention to the socio-economic, spiritual-moral, pedagogical-psychological aspects of professional change, the role of parents of the younger generation, the choice of school and independent life, and carefully follow the path of work in choosing a profession. Emphasized the need to learn awareness, observation and sequence, taking into account interest, predisposition and ability in directing the child to a career, in this regard, their age and personal characteristics. Hence, such examples indicate that our ancestors made a worthy contribution to the formation of the theory of career choice. There is no doubt that the use of the rich scientific heritage of our ancestors in the process of vocational education in secondary schools will work well.

Many examples of the dream of raising a harmonious generation can be given from our history. Al Farabi's "City of fertile people", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Qutadgü bilig", Kaykovus's "Qobusnoma", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibatul haqoyiq", Saadi's "Gulistan", Jami's "Baharistan", Alisher Nawai's "Mahbub ulqulub", Davani's "morals Jaloli" shed light on the meaning, ways, forms and ways of forming a healthy and harmonious person. One such work is Caicovus ' "Kabusnoma". The work "Qobusnoma", which has been a guide to preparing 49 peoples, especially young people, for life and practical activities since about a thousand years, has become an important place in bringing a person to spiritual perfection in the era of current changes. In the 82-83 years of the 12th century, Kaykovus ibn Iskandar, grandson of the king of western Iran, created his exhortation to his son Gilonshah, calling him "Qobusnoma" in honor of his grandfather King Shamsul maoniy Qobus. The work has been translated into many eastern and Western languages. In 1860, the work ' Kabusnoma " was first translated by the great Uzbek poet and thinker Muhammad Rizo Ogahi. This work consists of a preface and forty-four chapters. In the preface, he writes in the title of the work and the genealogy of the Ghilanshah, " O children, your own and your lineage from both sides are pure and exalted."

In the work of Kaykovus Kabusnoma, science is divided into three: the science associated with a profession, the profession associated with science, and the habit associated with charity and deed. The Taliban, who have entered the path of learning, are told to be dietary and rational all the time, to refrain from idleness, to be always cheerful and mobile, to give in to reading books, not to indulge in sadness in the path of science, to repeat it to keep Science in mind, to fight for truth in science, to say little and listen a lot. In a number of his works, Abu Nasr Farabi, the great allomah of the medieval East, promoted philosophical, scientific ideas about the mukaddash of Science and education, about gentleness, loyalty, humanity, upbringing, labor and vocational studies. For example: in his" brochure fit tanbih tool as-Saudat "(treatise on Ways To Achieve Happiness)," City of prosperous people " and other works, he details his dreams of a good, perfect, happy society. Raising a healthy and

harmonious generation has been the most cherished dream of mankind. A perfect person is understood as a person who has matured both mentally and morally and physically. The lexical meaning of the word perfect is also matured, matured, fluffy mature, in every way Full, perfect.

In conclusion, the issues of spiritual development of young students on the basis of our national spiritual heritage are gaining special relevance in the present day, when the Republic of Uzbekistan acquires state independence and is undergoing fundamental reforms in all spheres of social life. Because, in the spiritual education of young people, the social teaching of Eastern thinkers and the use of the legacy of the scholars of the Ma'mun Academy led to greater efficiency. Indeed, this spiritual heritage has tremendous opportunities in solving various pedagogical problems, and most importantly, in developing a spiritually harmonious person and thereby improving the quality of pedagogical training. Through the lessons of upbringing, the possibilities of introducing students to the advanced ideas and ideas of allomas that can serve as an example, an example of how young people should live, study and work; they are enriched with knowledge of how conscious thinkers operated in different socioeconomic conditions; students' understanding and vision of nurturing spiritual qualities is expanded. Students have developed a sense of pride in their great countrymen, scientists who have made a huge contribution to the development of world science, including upbringing; love for the Motherland, its interest in history, traditions increases; it is believed that the heritage of the great allomas of our people will be studied more independently. Development and introduction into life of an optimal system for the formation of a national idea in young people with the help of the study of the creativity of Eastern thinkers; - to cultivate a sense of interest in the realization of life, develop the ability to understand the complexity of the environment and human character; -to form a sense of loyalty to the motherland, to the people; - to organize classes with the help of didactic works of Eastern thinkers, taking into account the psychological characteristics of students; - to give special importance; - With the help of the creativity of our thinkers, the

goals and objectives of the formation of good qualities in students, ensuring the unity of content, forms and methods and maturing the personality of the reader.

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